

An Insight To Clear Aligners

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Abstract :

Several major developments have changed the field of orthodontics in the recent years. Digital imaging and computers have improved the diagnostic process. The introduction of prescription brackets, bonding, NiTi and other alloy wires have improved the treatment efficiency and efficacy. The paradigm shift in orthodontics arrived with the introduction of Aligner System. It allows both dental practitioner and patient to develop a visual understanding of orthodontic tooth movement. The esthetic and practical advantages of the system have extended orthodontic services to a greater population. This current review is to highlight the knowledge and application of clear aligners in not just simple but complicated malocclusion too, which is only possible with theoretical knowledge.

Keywords- Clear Aligner

Introduction

Adult patients seeking orthodontic treatment are increasingly motivated by aesthetic considerations. The majority of these patients reject wearing labial fixed steel appliances and are looking instead to more aesthetic treatment options, including ceramic brackets, lingual orthodontics and clear plastic appliances².

The two contemporary systems for moving the teeth with plastic appliances are the **Aligner & Essix System**³. The Aligner involves a series of aligners made from a transparent, thin (typically less than 1 mm) plastic material formed with CAD-CAM laboratory techniques. These aligners are similar to the splints that cover the clinical crowns and the marginal gingiva.

Each aligner is designed to move the teeth a maximum of about 0.25 to 0.3mm over a 2-week period, and is worn in a specific sequence. The Aligner System is unique in that the clinician must be able to plan the path to optimum results before treatment is initiated so that series of aligners can be constructed to achieve the treatment goals³. However, the Es six system is based on adjusting one single appliance to achieve the treatment goals³. Conventional fixed appliances are constantly undergoing in evolution because of use of multiple and different types of variables that

arise during treatment; so is it with Es six technology. Tooth movement is possible in all planes of space and the fabrication expense is a fraction of the cost of multiple laboratory fabricated appliances that must be used sequentially. Because Es six plastic appliances can be fabricated in the office, the cost of fabrication is minimal.

Clear plastic tooth moving appliances are excellent options for adults or responsible adolescents who might be reluctant to wear the fixed appliances and who will follow clinicians directions, and whose chief complaint centres around mild to moderate alignment problems. This discipline requires the essential elements of orthodontic tooth movement—force, space and time. The clinician can control two of these essential prerequisites—force and space. As with any dynamic removable appliance, the patient must provide the third essential – time. Therefore, the target population that is most eligible for tooth movement with plastic appliances are adults². Adolescents are usually not included in the plastic alignment population because strict adherence to clinical instructions is not predictable in that age group. Some clinicians believe that children and adolescents are best treated with conventional fixed appliance.

Discussion

The Aligner System influences visualization of treatment and timing of aligner and fixed appliances. Soft wears should be seen as a supplemental part of diagnosis and treatment planning and can help to clarify the relationship between vertical, transverse, and anteroposterior movements. It offers the orthodontist a new way of viewing treatment goals. Skeletal changes that can be performed easily in all soft wears are antero posterior corrections of the maxillary and mandibular Jaws.⁵⁻¹⁰

Clear aligner

In early 20th century, numerous advances in field of dentistry that have made a revolutionary changes in appliances and materials which led to change of perception amongst adult patient seeking orthodontic treatment with esthetic consideration, which has led to.

The theory of using an aligner to straighten teeth was first postulated in the 1940s when Kesling produced a tooth positioning appliance to refine the final stages of orthodontic treatment (Kesling, 1946)². This positioner was a piece of pliable rubber manufactured from a laboratory wax up of the teeth in a class I occlusion (Phan and Ling, 2007). This appliance allowed for minor tooth movements to be achieved while maintaining alignment of the remaining teeth in the arch. Tooth control was difficult, and only tipping of crowns was possible. Kesling foresaw that more ambitious tooth movements could be realized with a series of aligners, while recognizing the limitations of the technology available to him at the time: 'Major tooth movements could be accomplished with a series of positioners by changing the teeth on the set-up slightly as treatment progresses (Kesling, 1946)².

Thirty years later, Ponitz (1971)³ introduced an 'Invisible Retainer,' which used Kesling's idea of pre-positioning teeth on a master study model. Like Kesling's appliance, the 'Invisible Retainer' could only produce minor tooth movements, again achieving its results through the tipping of crowns.

In the early 90s, Sheridan described a technique of using clear aligners in conjunction with inter proximal tooth reduction Sheridan et al. (1993)⁶. The principle of producing minor tooth movements with individual aligners had not changed. A new 'Kesling set-up' was required for every tooth movement, and therefore, a new impression was taken at almost every visit. This process demanded a large amount of clinical and laboratory time. Align technology released their Aligner H system in 1999. It was the first orthodontic appliance to use computer-aided design (CAD) and computer-aided manufacturing (CAM). Instead of requiring a new impression for each tooth movement, this technology allows for multiple tooth set-ups to be created from a single impression (Hajeer et al., 2004)

Advantages

Today there is a high demand for an esthetic orthodontic appliance. Aligner offers the advantages of superior esthetics and comfort as compared to all other appliances currently available³⁹.

Esthetics:

Clear Aligner Therapy usually performs well in following condition:⁴³

- Mild crowded and mal aligned problems (1-5 mm)
- Spacing problems (1-5mm)
- Deep over bite (Class II div 2 cases)
- Narrow arches that can be expanded without tipping the teeth too much.
- Absolute intrusion (1 or 2 teeth)
- Lower incisor extraction for severe crowding cases
- Tip molar distally

Disadvantages

Use of the Aligner appliance is relatively new for orthodontists and is still being developed. Currently, few clinical studies and case reports have assessed the effectiveness of this technique. Although Align Technology has suggested guidelines for its appropriate use, clinicians have encountered numerous limitations when using the appliance.

Conditions that can be difficult to treat with an Inv is align appliance are:-

- Crowding and spacing over 5mm
- Skeletal anterior-posterior discrepancies of more than 2 mm (as measured by discrepancies in cuspid relationships)
- Centric-relation and centric-occlusion discrepancies
- Severely rotated teeth (more than 20 degrees)
- Open bites (anterior and posterior) that need to be closed
- Extrusion of teeth
- Severely tipped teeth (more than 45 degrees)
- Teeth with short clinical crowns
- Arches with multiple missing teeth.
- Prohibitively Expansive

In addition Clear Aligner therapy does not perform well in:

- Dental expansion or blocked-out teeth
- High canines
- Leveling by relative intrusion
- Molar uprighting (any teeth with large undercuts)
- Translation of molars
- Closure of premolar extraction spaces.

Tooth Movements With Aligner System

Bodily Tooth Movement

- Blocked-out incisor requires more space than can be obtained by stripping its proximal surfaces.
- Insert separators one contact away from the blocked-out incisor to create an open field for better visual access. See the patient no more than 5 days after placement.
- Use ARS to create space (0.5mm-.0mm).
- Use separators (slightly larger than in earlier Step) to move teeth into space created in previous step. Again, see the patient no more than 5 days after placement.
- Create a facial window (space within the appliance) for the tooth to move out of the blocked out position

Figure 1 –Bodily Tooth Movement

- Use Hilliard pliers to create force in 1mm increments to move the tooth into the facial window. axillary Pliers #82520 (bigger tip) is used for moving upper teeth. Mandibular Pliers #82530 (smaller tip) is used for moving lower teeth.
- 24-hour wear, except while eating, is recommended. Estimated results are 1mm per month.

Mesio-distal movement

- Triad gel #30009 s placed on the working model on the side of the tooth the lateral movement is to occur on. This creates a space, like a channel, in the thermo plastic for the tooth to move into when a force is created on the opposite side.
- This technique utilizes the Mesial- Distal Thermo pliers#82630
- The force for the desired movement is provided by either of the following methods:
 - A. A bump preparation in the plaster on the distal of the incisor.
 - B. A bump formed in the thermoplastic with the Mesial-DistalThermopliers after the appliance has been fabricated.

Figure 2 -Mesiodistal Movement

- Additional force from a larger bump in the thermoplastic (either at insertion or at subsequent adjustments) can be made with the appropriate Hilliard Thermopliers.
- The Bubble-Bump technique allows several teeth to be moved at the same time in the mesial distal direction. The capability to move in the mesial-distal direction can be combined with other movements on the same appliance to allow movement of teeth in all three planes of space.

Rotation

The depth and position of the bump and space in this technique are dictated by the amount of and type of rotation the clinician wants. This technique utilizes the micro-ramp Thermopliers #82560.

- Insert separators on either side of the tooth to create an open field for inter proximal reduction.
- Use ARS to create additional space between teeth.
- Construct an Es six appliance over the working cast.

Figure 3 -Rotation

Torquing

- Construct an Es six appliance over the working cast.
- Create space for the tooth to move leaving an incisa ledge cap.
- Using the maxillary Pliers #82520 place a 1mm bump near the gingival border. (For lower teeth, use the mandibular Pliers #82530) Use the micro-ramp Pliers #82560 o induce a bump close to the gingival margin if the maxillary and mandibular Pliers are tooththick.

Figure 4-Torquing

Anterior Intrusion

In order to intrude a tooth using an Es six appliance, relief must be provided on the lingual and labial surfaces of the target tooth in the appliance. Then a bump is created on the occlusal surface of the target tooth. The goal is to have light, continuous force on the target tooth as opposed to heavy pressure. The relief allows this to happen. Triad gel #30009s added to the working model to provide this relief.

Intrusion adjustments work well on a single tooth. It is possible to intrude two teeth at the same time but it becomes progressively more difficult to seat the appliance if more than two teeth are intruded at the same time.

Figure 5- Anterior Intrusion

It may be necessary to increase the retention of the Es six appliance if there is not sufficient retention.

The pathway for the tooth that is to be intruded needs to be clear of obstruction. ARS, separators or tooth movement may be necessary before the impression is taken for fabrication of the intrusion appliance

Bite Registration:

To accurately capture the occlusion of the two arches together, a bite registration is required. The bite registration is based on centric occlusion because a virtual typodont with a virtual hinge axis is not currently available

The Invisalign Process

The Invisalign process involves several steps. The first step is the gaining of complete patient records from the treating Orthodontist. Once received at Santa Clara the records go through a series of steps from scanning to case setup and then back to the clinician for a review called Clincheck. The process of manipulating virtual tooth movements is complete when the clinician approves the Clincheck. Once the Clincheck is approved, the aligners are processed and sent to the clinician.

Polyvinyl Siloxane (PVS) Impression:

An essential component of the Invisalign process is getting an accurate representation of the teeth. PVS was chosen because it provided the greatest degree of accuracy and stability. Tests are currently in progress to evaluate an alginate based material that can provide the accuracy and stability of PVS while allowing easier and the more efficient handling.

Figure 7- PVS registration

Scanning

Figure 6- One step PVS impression

Figure 8- Bite registration

Treats of Tware:

After the bite has been established, an Invisalign virtual orthodontic technician uses software to cut the virtual models and separate the teeth, thus allowing them to be moved individually.

In early 1997 the software component of Invisalign were broken into two parts: CLIPPER and ALIGNER. The clipper package allows a user to cut a virtual dental model into multiple pieces, each one representing a tooth. The aligner package takes the virtual model created by the clipper and allows a user to move the teeth in final position. Aligner also defines how the teeth will move into those positions overtime.

Figure 9- Early image with no virtual gingiva

Figure 10. Current image with virtual gingiva

Aligner Production:

Once the clinician approves the Clincheck, the three dimensional computer images are converted to physical models using a process called rapid proto typing. Specifically, stereo lithography is the rapid prototyping technology used to create the models. These models are used to fabricate the aligners on a Biostar (schue – dental) pressure molding machine.

The concept of moving teeth with clear overlay appliances has been around since 1926. Align technology is the first company to incorporate modern technology in a way that makes this concept a feasible, viable, efficient and effective orthodontic treatment option. The Invisalign process has evolved and improved since 1997 and even today continues to change and adapt to better meet the needs of clinicians and their patients.¹

Figure 11. Bio star machine

Figure 12. Stereo lithography model

Figure 13. Pressure-formed Aligner over the Stereo litho graphic model

Conclusion

In this era of 21st century, the number of adult patients seeking orthodontic treatment are increasing day by day. Fixed orthodontic appliance have been the spine of orthodontic bio mechanical technique. The appliances used today have evolved since Angles' Edgewise appliance. In 2017, White D. W, et al concluded in his study that Traditional fixed appliances produced significantly more discomfort than do aligners. During the first 3 days after bonding, there was significantly more discomfort when chewing than when at rest for patients treated with traditional appliances. Patients treated with aligners and traditional appliances reported significantly less discomfort at subsequent adjustments than after the initial bonding or appliance delivery.

In addition to this two major plastic tooth moving appliances, various other system like Clear Correct, MTM Clear Aligners, Clear Path Orthodontics, Clear Step, K-Ligner are promoting their plastic tooth moving appliances in various ways. This radical concept of esthetic plastic appliance for comprehensive orthodontic treatment needs additional research and refinement of the design which should allow further development of this worth while treatment.⁹

In Conclusion our findings are that Over the last 16 years, clear aligner treatment has developed from a technique of only treating mild crowding or spacing of anterior teeth to a technique that can be used to treat almost any type of orthodontic problem. However to do so, one needs to understand the limitations of the appliance and to able to think "out of the box" in treatment planning. Aligner materials and attachments will continue to improve which will allow aligners to fit better and for longer periods of time and result in better outcomes. Research into tooth movement and particularly tooth movement mechanics with aligners and the variation in these movements will allow further development of computer algorithms that are used in sequencing aligner tooth movement. Even so, with the amount of variation that is seen in orthodontic treatment, it will always take a knowledgeable practitioner to treatment plan and monitor treatment with alignes..

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